

Green Valorization of Floral Waste: Advancing Circular Economy Through Sustainable Resource Recovery

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Abstract

Floral waste from temples refers to the leftover flowers, garlands, and other plant materials that are used in religious rituals and offerings. In many cultures, particularly in Hinduism, Muslim, flowers play a significant role in worship and are commonly used to adorn deities, create garlands, and make offerings during wedding ceremony, decorations. After the rituals are completed, the remaining floral materials often become waste which promoting environment as a part of *India's Swachh Bharat programme*, for reducing the flower waste quantity and converting them into value added products. There are some standard disposal and treatment options, landfilling, incineration, dumping into the rivers, and composting which is controlled combustion of waste materials to a non-combustible residue or ash and exhaust gases. Floral waste offers numerous advantages including environmental benefits, economic benefits, and social benefits to reduce floral waste from the environment and degrade polluted. *Eisenia foetida* commonly known as the red wiggler was introduced into each packet, for vermicomposting process that converts floral waste into nutrient rich compost which improve soil fertility. Vermicompost obtained was analysed for various parameters like organic carbon, total nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, calcium, and magnesium. The amount of organic carbon, potassium and phosphorus was more in vermicompost samples for all the groups as compared to compost samples. Flowers like hibiscus, roses, and marigolds can be turned into beautiful, eco-friendly dyes. Floral wastes (FWs) clog the water channel and release pesticides, harming human beings and resident aquatic biota it left in landfills. Due to a lack of water bodies, flowers are left in landfills, which release methane, increase carbon emissions, and pollute the air and soil. Improper floral waste disposal leads to significant environmental problems, including water pollution, habitat damage, and the release of harmful chemicals, while also posing economic challenges by increasing waste management costs and hindering resource recovery.

Keywords: Swachh Bharat, Incineration, Non- Combustible, Biodegradable, *Eisenia foetida*, etc.

I. INTRODUCTION

India is a city with many temples, being visited by many devotees. These visitors or devotees come and offer floral garlands, fruits, coconut, sweets and other edibles to the God. The edibles are usually apart to be distributed among the devotees as Prasad and for consumption by priests, temple administrators and other staff. Non-consumable materials (floral garlands) are discarded as waste. Flowers are considered as holy entities and hence are offered by pilgrims to their idols (Bhati et al. 2021). Floral waste is generated by various sources like hotels, banquets, gardens, markets, marriage ceremony, and various others religious ceremony. Every day the flowers offered in the temples or used in the various ceremony or functions left unused and later it converted in to waste, and it becomes the major constituents of municipal solid waste (Singh et al. 2017). Every day these flowers offered in temples are left unexploited and therefore become solid waste. The collection and managing floral waste from temples are not only beneficial for the environment but also serves as an opportunity to engage the community in sustainable practices. Floral waste is biodegradable and contains elements required for growth of microorganisms. Floral waste can be repurposed into valuable products like compost, biofuel, organic fertilizers, incense sticks, soaps, and even handmade paper, contributing to a more sustainable and circular economy (Yadav et al. 2015). Initiatives that recycle flower waste can create meaningful employment opportunities, particularly for women. Utilizing flower waste promotes sustainable practices and reduces the environmental impact of the flower industry (Srivastav and kumar 2021). One of the most common ways to reuse flower waste is to add them to the compost bin and extract their nutrients to use in soil enrichment for the plant growth and crop improvement.

Figure 1: Managing of Floral waste for Generating Value-Added product

After the rituals are completed, the remaining floral materials often become waste. Just add the fresh, or dried, petals and leaves into the compost bin and leave it for weeks so that it decomposes well. The degradation of floral waste is a very slow process as compared to kitchen waste degradation by implementing effective collection systems, educating stakeholders (Jain 2016). In recent years, there has been a push in the floral industry towards sustainable practices and an environmental awareness of the impacts of the business given current production and management standards and strategies. Most of this waste is generally neglected and get added to water bodies which lead to water pollution (Mode et al. 2018). One of the main causes of environmental pollution is mismanagement of organic waste including temple waste, marriage ceremony, and other religious places (Mishra 2013). Solid or semi-solid waste disposal is a chief concern in India; harmless discarding of floral waste has been a cause of concern for the temple management. Worsening of environmental quality, climate change, disposal and management of waste and sustainable development are the chief issues to human society (Srivatava 2022). The efficient management of waste has further turned into one of the most significant problems of our time due to adjacent concerns regarding preservation of lifestyle, protection of the environment and promotion of public health (Chanu et al. 2023). Municipal solid waste is increasing enormously in every country with the expansion of population and there will be no shortage of raw materials to produce vermicompost. If left untreated, decomposing floral waste emits greenhouse gases such as methane, nitrous oxide, and fluorocarbons, increasing carbon emissions and polluting the air and soil.

Additionally, discarded flowers dumped into rivers negatively impact for aquatic life. However, these flowers can be transformed into valuable bio-products, including biogas, bioethanol, organic acids, perfumes, cosmetics, dyes, pigments, incense sticks, and biopolymers like polyhydroxybutyrate (PHB) and hydroxy valerate (Reddy and Sirisha 2024). Efficient floral waste management can significantly contribute to environmental sustainability while generating economic benefits through innovative waste recycling and bioprocessing techniques. The management of this waste, we can adopt sustainable techniques like vermicomposting as it is good for soil and promotes sustainable agriculture. On one hand, these wastes can be converted into agriculturally useful organic fertilizers which in turn have the potential to reduce the dependency on non-renewable chemical fertilizers and pesticides, and on the other hand, it controls waste which which is a major pollutant (Ahmed et al. 2021). It is well known that many of us avoid throwing the flowers and other items which are used in prayers in the garbage because of our religious beliefs and instead put them in the plastic bags and throw them directly into the water bodies. A portion of waste is thrown near sacred trees with no suitable mode of disposal. Such disposal of waste creates problems like worm development, foul odours, water pollution, and land pollution moreover it is not good aesthetically (Gpta et al. 2024).

Figure 2: (a) Openly disposed Floral Waste, (b) Floral Waste from Temple, (c) Shade drying of Floral Waste, (d) Sun drying of Floral Waste, (e) Oven drying Daisy Floral Waste, (f) Oven drying Rose Floral Waste, (g) After oven drying of Floral Waste, (h) Soil collect from the garden, (i) Adding cow dung into the soil, (j) To prepare a powder of floral waste for mixing the soil, (k) Add some Red wigglers (*Eisenia foetida*) for vermicomposting, (l) Mix the ingredients in the soil for composting, (m) Composting soil can be drying and grinding, (n) To test carbon in the soil, (o) To test nitrogen in the soil, (p) To test electrical conductivity of the soil, (q) To test temperature by thermometer of the soil,

(r) To test pH of the soil, (s) Observe the growth generation of seed growth 10 days, (t) Monitoring the plant growth by using nutrients

Problem statement the current linear economy model leads to significant environmental problems due to the disposal of floral waste, including water pollution and disruption of aquatic ecosystems. Valorising floral waste, transforming it into valuable products, can contribute to a circular economy, reducing waste, minimizing environmental impact, and creating economic opportunities. This problem statement focuses on identifying the challenges and opportunities in developing and implementing floral waste valorisation practices within a circular economy framework. The urgent need to develop and implement effective floral waste management strategies that minimize environmental impact, protect human health, and promote sustainable practices. Objectives of the Study: This research aims to assess the current state of floral waste generation and disposal practices in India. Explore sustainable waste management strategies for recycling floral waste into bio-based products. Evaluate the economic feasibility and scalability of floral waste-based industries. Highlight the environmental benefits of converting floral waste into value-added products. Propose policy recommendations and community-driven initiatives for large-scale floral waste recycling to scale up recycling technologies.

II METHODOLOGY

2.1 Collection of Flower Waste from Temples

The flower waste used in this study was collected from Devkali Mandir, situated near the Yamuna River in district Auraiya, Uttar Pradesh, India. This temple is in the southern direction from the district headquarters of Auraiya, at 26.470112° N latitude and 79.519876° E longitude. As one of the major religious sites in the region, a large quantity of floral waste is generated daily through offerings made by devotees (Mode et al. 2018). The floral waste was gathered carefully in polythene bags and transported to the laboratory for further processing. The waste primarily included marigold (*Tagetes* spp.), rose (*Rosa* spp.), and daisy (*Bellis perennis*) flowers. These species were chosen due to their frequent use in religious rituals and their prevalence among floral offerings (Titikshya et al. 2024). Additionally, soil sample were collected from various locations within a nearby agricultural field to ensure a representative mix of indigenous microbial communities. The aim was to isolate natural microbial strains capable of efficiently degrading floral biomass (Singh et al. 2017; Adhikary and Vishwavidyalaya 2020). Soil is a complex mixture composed of approximately 45% mineral particles, 5% organic matter, 20–30% water, and 20–30% air. These proportions provide a conducive environment for microbial activity, essential for composting. In India, flowers play a deeply meaningful role in daily life, from religious offerings and celebrations to making garlands, decorative items, and even traditional medicines. However, all these activities generate a significant amount of floral waste, much of which ends up in landfills or polluting water bodies. Rather than seeing this as a problem, it can be viewed as an opportunity for sustainable action. Floral waste, rich in proteins, lipids, carbohydrates, essential oils, minerals, and vitamins, holds untapped potential. Instead of being discarded, these flowers can be managed responsibly using the three Rs—Reduce, Reuse, and Recycle. For example, digital offerings can help minimize the physical use of flowers in religious rituals, while biodegradable materials can replace synthetic ones in floral decorations. One of the most promising approaches lies in composting. Floral waste can be turned into vermicompost, enriching the soil and promoting eco-friendly agriculture. It can also serve as a natural biosorbent to clean pollutants from water and soil, offering an environmentally sound alternative to chemical treatments.

Table 1. The Technologies available for Floral Waste process involved and the product evolved

Sources of Floral Waste	Environmental Impact	Product/Process	Technologies Available	Technology Provider
Temples	Water Pollution	Incense stick from Flower waste	Technology for utilization of waste	CSIR- Central Institute of Medicinal and Aromatic Plants, Lucknow Website: www.cimap.res.in
Weddings	Improper disposal of flower waste	Artistic greeting cards, wall plates, landscapes, three dimensional interior decorative items, etc	Dehydration of flowers and foliage technologies	CSIR- National Botanical Research Institute, Lucknow Website: www.nbri.res.in
Festivals	Land Pollution	Natural Dye	Eco-friendly dyeing and antibacterial finishing of soya bean protein fabric using waste flowers from temples	Department of Fibers and Textile Processing Technology, Institute of Chemical Technology, Mumbai
Hotels	Composting	Vermicomposting of Temple waste is an excellent and eco-friendly method of temple waste management	Production of Vermicompost from Temple Waste	Department of Microbiology. K.W. College and Department of Biotechnology, Fergusson College, Maharashtra
Gardens	Soil Degradation	Vermicomposting of Flower waste, into a nutrient rich compost	Utilization of Temple waste flower for dyeing of Cotton, Wool and Silk on industrial scale	Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur

2.2 Extraction and Preprocessing of Flower Waste

Upon arrival at the laboratory, the collected floral waste underwent an initial manual segregation process. Non-biodegradable materials such as plastic, paper, thread, and wires were meticulously removed by hand-sorting to ensure the purity of the organic fraction (Dutta et al. 2021; Gupta et al. 2024). Only the biodegradable components, particularly flower petals and floral remains, were retained for further processing. All stems, roots, and leaves were excluded from the composting process to focus entirely on floral material. The selected flower waste was washed thoroughly using tap

water to remove residues of pesticides, herbicides, fertilizers, and dust particles, which could interfere with microbial degradation or compost quality (Etheredge and Waliczek 2022). A critical step in preprocessing involved removing lignin-rich parts, as lignin slows down the degradation process due to its complex polymeric structure (Goel and kulshrestha 2024). To improve compost ability, visible lignin-rich structures were removed manually, and the remaining material was subjected to drying using three methods:

- Sun drying, using natural sunlight over several days,
- Oven drying using controlled temperature to remove moisture,
- Shade drying where flower waste was dried in a well-ventilated room.

These methods helped reduce the moisture content of the floral waste, improve shelf life, and facilitate storage and processing. The dried flower waste was then crushed using a mixer grinder to obtain a homogenized floral paste, suitable for blending with composting materials (Srivastav and kumar 2021). This paste served as the primary organic input for the preparation of compost in the next stage.

2.3 Preparation of organic manure (Hot Composting Method)

For the preparation of organic manure, the hot composting technique was utilized to accelerate the degradation of floral biomass. Composting was conducted in grow bags, which provided a compact and manageable space for thermal composting (Waqas et al. 2021). Initially, each grow bag was half-filled with field soil, providing a microbial base and structural support. To balance the carbon-to-nitrogen ratio, sawdust (as a carbon source) and cow dung (as a nitrogen source and microbial inoculant) were added (Mulay et al. 2020; Jain 2016). The homogenized floral paste was then incorporated and thoroughly mixed with the other components. Maintaining the correct balance of moisture and aeration was essential to support microbial activity (Kumari et al. 2021). The mixture was kept moist but not waterlogged, with water added periodically to maintain a moisture level of around 50-60%. The composting mass naturally entered the thermophilic phase within a few days, during which internal temperatures rose to 54–71°C (131–160°F) (Hujuri et al. 2023; Kumari et al.2021).

Table 2. Experimental Design for Vermicomposting

S.NO.	Experimental Design	Details
1.	Group 1- 50:50	Quadruplicates (750gm Daisy Flower Waste + 750gm soil + 300 Cow dung + 100gm Earthworms)
2.	Group 2- 50:50	Quadruplicates (750gm Rose Flower Waste + 750gm soil + 300 Cow dung + 100gm Earthworms)
3.	Group 3- 50:50	Quadruplicates (750gm Marigold Flower Waste + 750gm soil + 300 Cow dung + 100gm Earthworms)
4.	Group 4- 50:50	Triplicates (750gm soil + 300gm Cow dung + 100gm Earthworms)

These high temperatures promoted the growth of thermophilic microbes, which rapidly broke down the organic material. This phase was sustained for the first 3 to 4 weeks of composting. To facilitate uniform decomposition and heat distribution, the contents of the grow bags were manually turned every 3 to 4 days (Mitali and Amita 2015). This

aeration process ensured oxygen availability and prevented anaerobic zones that could cause foul odours or slow down composting. After the thermophilic stage, the compost entered the cooling and maturation phase, marked by a decrease in temperature and stabilization of the compost material (Kadir et al. 2017). During this phase, mesophilic microorganisms resumed activity and completed the degradation process, resulting in a nutrient-rich, dark brown compost (Sharma et al. 2017).

Vermicomposting, the process of using worms (*Eisenia fetida*) to compost organic matter, is generally faster than traditional composting, often taking 2-3 months to produce finished compost. Worms can process food waste and other organic materials much quicker than traditional methods, which can take 6-9 months. Earthworms are known for their ability to consume and digest organic material, and their excrement, known as vermicast, is rich in nutrients and beneficial microorganisms. Verm cast is a dark, nutrient-rich soil amendment that can be used to improve soil health and plant growth. Once the compost resembles dark, rich soil with a crumbly, loose texture and smell like fresh soil.

2.4 Seed Germination and Plant Growth Monitoring

To evaluate the effectiveness of floral compost prepared using the hot composting method (kept at room temperature), an experiment was conducted by planting spinach (*Spinacia oleracea*) and moong (*Vigna radiata*) seeds. These crops were selected due to their short life cycles, high sensitivity to soil conditions, and significance in nutrition and local agriculture.

Table 3. Application of Floral Waste in Composting studies

Name of Flower	Scientific Name	Application	References
Marigold	<i>Tagetes erecta</i>	Adding both nutrient and pest repellent	Mode et al. 2018
Daisy	<i>Bellis perennis</i>	Source of Organic Matter to soil health and crop yield	Sharma et al. 2017
Rose	<i>Rosa rubiginosa</i>	To create a valuable fertilizer for various plants	Dutta and Kumar 2022

2.5 Seed Preparation and Sowing

Before sowing, the seeds were carefully surface sterilized using a mild sodium hypochlorite solution to prevent any microbial contamination and ensure uniform sprouting. They were then thoroughly rinsed with clean water. Compost prepared from temple floral waste was mixed with garden soil in an approximate 2:1 ratio and filled into grow bags. Another set of grow bags filled with only natural garden soil acted as the control group. Each grow bag was sown with an equal number of seeds for both spinach and moong, and all grow bags were maintained under identical environmental conditions. Regular watering was done using equal volumes of water, and the containers were kept in well-lit areas with proper ventilation.

2.6 Determination of physicochemical parameters

The matured vermicompost samples about 500 gm were collected in Ziploc polythene bags labelled and sealed air tightly these bags are free from adventitious contaminations and were brought to the laboratory for investigation.

2.6.1 Physical Parameters

The temperature was measured during the composting interval using the mercury thermometer. Various types of the grow bags samples were measured, and average temperature was calculated. Moisture content of sample was reported to first 15 days and the moisture content adjusted range between the 70-80% when the grow bags were dried. For determination of the moisture content of the sample, the gravimetric method was used (Prajapati et al. 2022; Sharma and Yadav et al. 2017). For calculating the pH 2 g of dried samples were diluted by 20 ml distilled water (1:10 w/ v) and samples were kept on rotary shaker for 60 to 90 min, then allow for settle down, and after that filtered through *Whatman filter paper No. 42* (Singh et al. 2016).

2.6.2 Chemical Parameters

By using Kjeldahl method, total nitrogen content was determined. The macronutrients like P and K and the micronutrients, viz., Fe, Mn, Zn and Cu were determined based on the method of Singh and Kalamdhad (2012). Before the analysis, digested samples were heated by 0.05 g dry sample with proportion of 5:1 of 15 ml of H₂SO₄ and HClO₄ at 335 and 203°C for general 120 min. These digested samples were used for calculating the total phosphorous by using stannous chloride method (Dwivedi et al., 2019; Vankar 2009). Na and K concentration were determined by using flame photometer. The micro and macronutrients were determined by the Atomic Spectroscopy method Mary and Janthark (2023).

2.6.3 Growth Parameters

The plants were harvested, and their growth parameters were analysed. At the end of the experiment total fresh weight, length of shoots and roots per plant were determined by using method of Patel et al. 2023. Moong thrives in hot, dry climates with loamy or light sandy loam soil, a pH between 6.5 and 7.5, and a temperature between 30-40°.

2.7 Monitoring and Observations

Seed germination was observed visually daily. The appearance of the first sprouts in the floral compost mixture occurred earlier than those in the control setup. Germination was more uniform in the compost-based setup, with healthier initial shoots and leaves. Over the next few weeks, plant development was continuously monitored. Plants grown in the floral compost mixture exhibited faster growth, greener leaves, and greater overall vigour. The root systems were more developed and fibrous, indicating a better nutrient absorption environment. The compost provided an aerated and microbially active substrate that supported healthy root formation and shoot elongation. In contrast, the plants grown in regular soil without compost showed slower growth, thinner stems, and lighter leaf colour, suggesting limited nutrient availability and suboptimal soil conditions.

2.8 Plant Growth and Soil Impact

The compost-enriched soil maintained better moisture retention and a looser structure, supporting plant growth without waterlogging. The pleasant, earthy smell and crumbly texture of the compost also indicated complete

decomposition and microbial balance. The decomposition of flower waste, especially marigold and rose petals, seemed to contribute not only organic matter but also micronutrients essential for early plant development. Additionally, the absence of stems, plastic, thread, and pesticide residues ensured that the compost was free from toxins that could hinder germination or root formation.

III. RESULTS

3.1 Initial characteristics of waste materials

During the setup of the grow bags, some common features were noted in the mixtures of various flowers of various flower wastes. Most important among these were the high moisture levels in the mixtures that resulted in lumps and the presence of leachate. To facilitate the compost to develop the thermophilic stage in a short while preferably one to two days the polythene sheets covered the grow bags. This covering had a double benefit: it facilitated the trapping of heat and raising the levels of internal humidity. Consequently, water vapours started collecting on the inner polythene, indicating an increase in heat and humidity, both of which are vital conditions for initiating bacterial growth.

Table 4. Initial properties of the collected flower waste during composting

Parameters	Rose flower waste	Daisy flower waste	Marigold flower waste	Without flower waste
Moisture content (%)	78	76	78	70
pH	6.71	7.02	6.74	7.15
Electrical Conductivity (mS cm ⁻¹)	0.98	0.22	0.57	0.22
Total Organic Carbon (%)	0.66	0.81	1.11	0.52
Total Nitrogen (%)	271.6	283.50	357.50	264.3
C:N ratio	0.0024	0.0028	0.0031	0.0019
Phosphorus (g kg ⁻¹)	14.24	16.00	18.1	13.8
Potassium (g kg ⁻¹)	0.52	0.89	1.01	0.48

An increased temperature is important because it favours the microbial action required for effective composting. Specifically, water vapours' presence plays a significant role in degrading more persistent compounds like lignin and tannins, hence accelerating the entire degradation process (Varma and Kalamdhad, 2014b). To facilitate sufficient supply of oxygen another significant factor for robust composting the mixtures were well turned and mixed every two to three days. This aeration further increased the internal temperature of the pits, allowing for continued microbial activity. All the important parameters temperature, moisture content, and decomposition rate were regularly monitored and documented at ten-day intervals during the composting duration. This scientific observation assisted in monitoring the alterations and comprehending the composting processes in detail.

3.2 Temperature (°C)

Temperature is an important factor in the activation and development of microbial growth during composting. During the composting process, the temperature within each grow bag fluctuated, as shown in Figure 3. All grow bags ultimately entered the cooling and maturation stages. Composting process often begins with the mesophilic phase (10°C to 40°C), where the mesophilic microorganisms are activated and start decomposing easily degradable materials (Varma and Kalamdhad, 2014b). With increased microbial activity, temperature increases, moving into the thermophilic phase (45°C to 71°C). In this phase, thermophilic bacteria prevail, mixing the decomposition of organic matter. But others of the grow bags failed to achieve the thermophilic stage due to having very high moisture content, which provided undesirable conditions for microbial development (Abdullah et al., 2013). Of all the configurations, the Daisy and Marigold grow bags exhibited the greatest thermophilic activity. This achievement was credited to the ideal composition of cow dung, flower residues, and inclusion of earthworms.

Figure 3: Different temperatures during composting time

These two configurations achieved maximum temperatures of 34°C and 38°C respectively, which can be attributed to the highly balanced ratios of the prepared waste mixes (Singh and Kalamdhad, 2014). The temperatures varied between 25°C and 35°C in the initial 10 days high enough to kill off pathogens and provide sanitation for the compost (Awasthi et al. 2015). Comparable temperature trends have been seen in other studies on composting using other types of waste. Adding Moong and Spinach seeds to floral waste compost can lead to unwanted germination if the compost pile doesn't reach a high temperature to kill the seeds. While Moong seeds germinate best at Marigold, Daisy, and Rose 35°C to 38°C and Spinach seeds germinate best at Daisy and Marigold 29°C to 34°C.

3.3 Moisture content (%)

During the first stage of composting, the moisture content in the grow bags differed according to the type of flower waste. Daisy flower waste contained 76.05% moisture, rose flower waste contained an abnormally high reading of 78.32% (presumably a typographical error), marigold flower waste contained 78.67%, and the control bag with no flower waste contained 70.89%. In the course of time, moisture content in all grow bags dropped consistently (Mode et al. 2018). Figure 3 shows the moisture content differences among the different grow bag treatments. Cow dung was used as a microbial inoculum to stimulate microbial activity; it has high moisture content ensuring that adequate moisture levels are maintained in the compost mixture. Earthworms require moist conditions too, which play a key function in vermicomposting. Earthworms regulate moisture through the process of decomposing organic matter and eliminating nutrient-rich castings. Care should be exercised, though: too much water leads to anaerobic environments, which adversely affect worms as well as microbe populations. In flower waste-based vermicomposting systems that also incorporate cow dung and earthworms, the moisture level is usually kept at 40% to 60% for the seed generation. This allows for effective composting and facilitates the decomposition of organic matter. Monitoring and adjusting on time are important to establishing a good composting environment that encourages microbial growth as well as as earthworm activity.

3.4 Electrical conductivity and pH

Figure 5a: Effect of electrical conductivity during 3 - 4 weeks Composting time

Figure 5b: Effect of electrical conductivity during Seed Generation

Figure 6: Different ranges of pH during Composting time

Throughout the initial 20 days of composting, the pH levels increase gradually. At around 40 days, the pH changes started to become less significant. Towards the end of the 80-day duration, the pH values in the compost in different grow bags varied between 4 and 8, which means that the compost may range from acidic to neutral to even slightly alkaline. Turning of the compost on a regular basis contributed to the rise in pH as it enhanced the flow of oxygen, thereby promoting stable aerobic conditions (Awasthi et al. 2015). The tendencies align with other researchers who

have worked on composting organic waste (Kalamdhad and Kazmi, 2009; Mena et al., 2003). In the last phase, the pH of the compost usually stabilized between 6 and 8, an optimum for nutrient absorption. A pH below 6 can restrict the availability of some nutrients such as phosphorus. At a pH above 7.5, it tends to cause micronutrient deficiencies (Varma and Kalamdhad, 2014a). Moreover, microbial activity, which is central to composting, has direct relationships with pH levels. Adding Moong and Spinach seeds to floral waste compost involves a natural breakdown of organic matter, and the pH can fluctuate. The compost's pH towards a slightly alkaline range, as the seeds release minerals during decomposition.

Figures 4a, 4b, and 5 show the pH and electrical conductivity variations during the composting process. Electrical conductivity is a measure of the salinity of the compost and is also an indicator of nutrient availability. The values varied between 0.32 and 0.87 mS/cm, and lower values indicated low nutrient levels and higher values nutrient-rich compost, which is generally good for plant growth including Moong and Spinach. But d Spinach. But slightly saline is detrimental to plants (Huang et al. 2004). Electrical conductivity of compost was initially relatively moderate, a condition that is appropriate for the composting of flower waste. As the activity progressed to the thermophilic stage during which microbial work and temperature were at their highs conductivity rose. There is extensively breakage of the organic matter that led to conductivity rose. There was extensive breakage of the organic matter led to liberation of mineral salts, such as ammonium and phosphate, thus causing conductivity levels to rise (Yadav et al., 2013). It's also worth mentioning also worth mentioning that composting flower waste alone might not lead to effective degradation waste alone might not lead to effective degradation because of its high-water content and lower temperatures.

3.5 Total carbon content

Figure 7a: Effect of organic carbon during composting time

Figure 7b: Effect of organic carbon during seed generation

The reduction in the concentration of carbon throughout composting is one of the most significant indicators of compost maturity. As indicated by Figure 7a and 7b, the content of total organic carbon reduced from day to day for all composting arrangements, including Daisy, Rose, and Marigold floral wastes, and even in a control without floral waste. Of these, the compost comprising Rose floral waste had the minimum decrease in total organic carbon. This may be attributed to the reduced rate of decomposition of organic material by microorganisms that utilize carbon as a source of energy when breaking down. When compost ages, microbial respiration depletes available carbon, causing its continuous reduction. The decomposition phase is responsible to a large degree for settling levels of carbon. More carbon will be present in fresh floral garbage than in complete compost. A mix of other organic matter like kitchen scraps, leaves, or grass clippings with floral waste will be subject to carbon content variations.

The right mixture of carbonated and nitrogen-based materials is a requirement for efficient composting. Moisture content also affects carbon measurement. Excessive moisture can water down carbon concentration when calculated as a percentage of total weight. During the composting process, microbial decomposition of organic matter changes carbon levels as these microorganisms use carbon for growth and energy. The carbon content in compost influences both its nutrient quality and ability to promote plant growth. A suitable carbon to nitrogen ratio ensures a high-quality, structured compost that also improves soil oxygenation and water holding capacity vital in grow bags where root conditions are paramount. Composting floral waste is one way of practising sustainable horticulture by recycling organic and biodegradable waste and avoiding organic waste accumulation. Notably, phenolic acids and lignin present in roses can determine microbial activity and temperature levels in the process of composting and, by extension, the way carbon is decomposed.

Marigold waste, however, decomposes more easily because it has a less complex organic composition and contains thermophilic bacteria. These conditions resulted in greater total organic carbon content in Daisy and Marigold

composts, which were responsible for protein degradation and breaking down complex cellulose. The same conclusion has been established by Awasthi et al. (2015) and Zhou et al. (2014), with observations of organic carbon decreases when organic waste became more mature in the process of mineralization. The range experienced in carbon level (0.55%) relatively shows the low carbon content in standard, this means the compost is not as nutrient rich as expected in floral waste compost when applied in bags and high carbon content in Daisy compost, Marigold compost, and Rose compost range is (0.66% to 1.11%). However, the low carbon content indicating the floral waste has already undergone some decomposition and is relatively stable. These considerations are central in creating high grade compost that optimizes plant establishment and soil functioning. Adding Moong and Spinach seeds in the Daisy compost, Rose compost, and Marigold compost, may provide a suitable environment for growth, nutrients are adequately supplied.

3.6 Macronutrient and Micronutrient

Figure 7(a): Nitrogen variation during compost waste

Figure 7(b): Nitrogen variation during Seed Generation

Figure 8(a): Variation of phosphorus in compost during initial stage

Figure 8(b): Variation of phosphorus during Seed Generation

The microbial metabolism and healthy plant growth depend greatly on macronutrients obtained from organic matter. As indicated in Figure 7a, the overall nitrogen content in organic compost increases with time. The nitrogen content in the compost was at its minimum at the beginning, but it increased tremendously by the time the compost was mature enough to be used in grow bags. This pattern is in line with that documented by Jolanun and Towprayoon (2010), who found comparable rises in total nitrogen when composting. With maturation of compost, decomposition of organic material and carbon loss are responsible for an overall increase in nitrogen content. Garcia et al. (1992) also documented this phenomenon. The nitrogen level of Moong and Spinach seeds compost varied between 264.3 and 357.50 ppm (or mg/kg), indicates a high level of nitrogen, which should be beneficial for both seeds. A greater concentration of nitrogen tends to increase the quality of the compost, supporting healthy plant growth when applied in grow bags. Yet, one needs to control nitrogen concentrations tightly too much can cause issues such as nutrient burn or excessively or leafy foliage, which might be at the expense of flowering or fruiting. Moong beans will benefit as well, though they may not require as much external nitrogen due to their nitrogen fixing capabilities. Spinach will likely thrive in this nitrogen rich environment, leading to lush green leaves.

Phosphorus content was determined to increase slowly from the start to the end of the composting process in all treatments Daisy compost, Rose compost, Marigold compost, and the control without flower waste. Of these, compost made with Marigold compost had the highest phosphorus content, followed by Daisy, Rose, and then the control. This increase in phosphorus content can be explained by the decomposition of organic matter during composting, which concentrates the nutrient in the product of compost. These findings were corroborated by Singh et al. (2014) and Varma and Kalamdhad (2014a) who reported higher phosphorus content in floral waste, earthworm, and cow dung composts. These results are demonstrated in Figure: 8a, 8b, where the variations in phosphorus content during composting are indicated. Potassium concentrations also appreciably at the completion of composting in all treatments of flower waste Marigold, Daisy, Rose and in the control. The elevated levels of potassium indicate that flower waste is inherently rich in this nutrient, leading to potassium rich compost. Microbial activity supports the enrichment, as it mobilizes and assimilates potassium in the compost material (Singh et al., 2012). Figure 8b illustrates these potassium variations. When Spinach and Moong seeds were sown in grow bags containing the treated composts, phosphorus contents were comparatively in the middle level, and it is apt for root development as well as overall plant growth. Especially in the combinations Daisy-Moong, Marigold-Moong, and Marigold-Spinach, there was maximum phosphorus availability for good plant growth.

3.7 C:N ratio

The carbon-to-nitrogen ratio (C: N) is one of the important indicators during the composting process, commonly employed nowadays to measure compost maturity (Jiang et al. 2011; Huang et al. 2004). It is an important factor in defining the decomposition rate of organic matter and the final quality of the compost. Lower C:N ratio generally indicates more nitrogen content, which can intensify microbial growth and hasten the composting process. Through out composting, C:N ratio occurs naturally to drop because overall organic carbon decreases a nitrogen increases. In this experiment, compost materials of Daisy, Marigold, Rose, and a Standard compost all evidenced a reduction of their C:N ratios over the passage of time, reflecting compost maturation. On completion of composting time, the following C:N ratios were measured.

Daisy compost (0.0028): This reflected balanced carbon and nitrogen composition, aiding in constant microbial decomposition. Rose compost (0.0024): With a lower C:N ratio than Daisy, Rose compost contained more nitrogen, probably permitting quicker breakdown and producing a more nutrient-rich compost. Marigold compost (0.0031): The highest C:N ratio of the three, indicating more carbon compared to nitrogen. This compost could break down slowly and might appreciate added nitrogen to maximize microbial efficiency. Standard compost (0.0019): With the lowest ratio, this compost was very nitrogen-rich, making it highly decomposable and potentially excellent for plant growth. With the introduction of seeds for germination, C:N ratios N ratios varied slightly from 0.0022 in Standard Moong and Spinach composts to 0.0026 in Marigold-Spinach, Daisy-Moong-Spinach, and Rose-Moong-Spinach mixtures and Marigold-Moong 0.0028. This decrease is due to microbial activity microorganisms utilize carbon as a source of energy while utilizing nitrogen for cell structure, hence decreasing the overall C:N ratio (Yadav et al., 2011; Adhikari et al., 2009; Yadav et al., 2009). Interestingly, compost without floral waste, like the Standard Moong and Spinach, indicated a lower decline in organic carbon and a steady rise in nitrogen content, slightly increasing the C:N ratio. All these findings indicate that the presence of floral waste significantly contributes to greater organic carbon degradation, which further facilitates compost maturation and proper seed germination.

IV. DISCUSSION

The flower waste plays a key role in the growth and the development of seed which depends on both physical and chemical properties of the soil, like soil temperature, moisture, pH and many physicochemical properties. Marigold and Daisy observed maximum temperature that is 40 and 38°C, respectively among all grow bags. During the ten days, temperature varies from the range between 25 and 35°C which is responsible for all to kill the pathogen and sanitized the compost (Awasthi et al., 2015). The similar findings were found by (Singh et al. 2014); Varma and Kalamdhad (2014); Abdullah et al. (2013) for the various composting waste. Linearly decrease the moisture content of Daisy and Marigold flower waste respectively. The prepared compost, after 15 days of composting, the pH was changed at 5.28 to 7.5. Continuous mixing the compost during the composting which increases the pH which ultimately maintains the oxygen supply to stabilize the aerobic condition (Awasthi et al., 2015). Earthworm accelerates the mineralisation rate and converts the waste into casting with higher nutritional value and degree of humification (Kalamdhad and Kazmi 2009); (Mena et al. 2003).

Table 5: Observations of Seed Growth

Compost Type	Moong Growth	Spinach Growth	Observation
Daisy	Yes	Yes	Growth observed
Rose	Yes	Yes	Growth Observed
Marigold	Yes	Yes	Growth observed
Standard	No	No	Inhibited or no growth

Flower composts from Daisy, Rose, and Marigold seem to foster healthier soil, possibly because they have a better soil, possibly because they have a better carbon-to-nitrogen (C: N) ratio, there is active microbial life, and there are natural aromatic compounds. All these conditions combined seem to enhance seed germination and seedling growth. The Standard compost did not help plant growth, indicating that perhaps it had not decomposed sufficiently. It could

be that this compost is still full of raw or partly decomposed material, too alkaline or acidic, or contain high levels of salts or heavy metals. Alternatively, it may just not contain the necessary nutrients that young plants require to grow.

V. CONCLUSION

This phase of the study demonstrated that even without the application of hot composting methods, floral waste compost prepared at room temperature can effectively support plant germination and growth. The spinach and moong plants thrived in the compost-enhanced soil, confirming the organic manure's ability to act as a nutrient-rich and eco-friendly alternative to synthetic fertilizers. This validates the practical utility of floral waste recycling as a sustainable and accessible practice for improving soil fertility and promoting green agriculture. The study suggests that composts derived specifically from Daisy, Rose, and Marigold floral wastes are effective in promoting early seedling development in Moong and Spinach. However, the Standard compost was unsuitable, possibly due to incomplete decomposition or nutrient imbalance.

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